

ESLint categories

Possible Errors

These rules relate to possible syntax or logic errors in JavaScript code.

Best Practices

These rules relate to better ways of doing things to help you avoid problems.

Strict Mode

These rules relate to strict mode directives.

Variables

These rules relate to variable declarations.

Node.js and CommonJS

These rules relate to code running in Node.js, or in browsers with CommonJS.

Stylistic Issues

These rules relate to style guidelines, and are therefore quite subjective.

ECMAScript 6

These rules relate to ES6, also known as ES2015.

Configurations for the category *Possible Errors*

errors

warnings

allows

(bold) in eslint:recommended

Uses	Does not use
no-cond-assign no-console no-constant-condition no-control-regex no-debugger no-dupe-args no-dupe-keys no-duplicate-case no-empty-character-class no-empty no-ex-assign no-extra-boolean-cast no-extra-semi no-func-assign no-inner-declarations no-invalid-regexp no-irregular-whitespace no-obj-calls no-regex-spaces no-sparse-arrays no-unreachable use-isnan valid-typeof	no-await-in-loop no-extra-parens no-prototype-builtins no-template-curly-in-string no-unexpected-multiline no-unsafe-finally no-unsafe-negation valid-jsdoc

Configurations for the category *Best Practices*

Uses	Does not use
<p>no-fallthrough no-octal no-redeclare</p>	<p>accessor-pairs array-callback-return block-scoped-var class-methods-use-this complexity consistent-return curly default-case dot-location dot-notation eqeqeq guard-for-in no-alert no-caller no-case-declarations no-div-regex no-else-return no-empty-function no-empty-pattern no-eq-null no-eval no-extend-native no-extra-bind no-extra-label no-floating-decimal no-global-assign no-implicit-coercion no-implicit-globals no-implied-eval no-invalid-this no-iterator no-labels no-lone-blocks no-loop-func no-magic-numbers no-multi-spaces no-multi-str no-new-func</p>

no-new-wrappers
no-new
no-octal-escape
no-param-reassign
no-proto
no-restricted-properties
no-return-assign
no-return-await
no-script-url
no-self-assign
no-self-compare
no-sequences
no-throw-literal
no-unmodified-loop-condition
no-unused-expressions
no-unused-labels
no-useless-call
no-useless-concat
no-useless-escape
no-useless-return
no-void
no-warning-comments
no-with
radix
require-await
vars-on-top
wrap-iife
yoda

Configurations for the category *Variables*

Uses	Does not use
no-delete-var no-undef no-unused-vars	init-declarations no-catch-shadow no-label-var no-restricted-globals no-shadow-restricted-names no-shadow no-undef-init no-undefined no-use-before-define

Configurations for the category *Stylistic Issues*

Uses	Does not use
<p>quotes</p> <p>no-mixed-spaces-and-tabs</p> <p>comma-dangle</p>	<p>array-bracket-spacing</p> <p>block-spacing</p> <p>brace-style</p> <p>camelcase</p> <p>capitalized-comments</p> <p>comma-spacing</p> <p>comma-style</p> <p>computed-property-spacing</p> <p>consistent-this</p> <p>eol-last</p> <p>func-call-spacing</p> <p>func-name-matching</p> <p>func-names</p> <p>func-style</p> <p>id-blacklist</p> <p>id-length</p> <p>id-match</p> <p>indent</p> <p>jsx-quotes</p> <p>key-spacing</p> <p>keyword-spacing</p> <p>line-comment-position</p> <p>linebreak-style</p> <p>lines-around-comment</p> <p>lines-around-directive</p> <p>max-depth</p> <p>max-len</p> <p>max-lines</p> <p>max-nested-callbacks</p> <p>max-params</p> <p>max-statements-per-line</p> <p>max-statements</p> <p>multiline-ternary</p> <p>new-cap</p> <p>new-parens</p> <p>newline-after-var</p> <p>newline-before-return</p> <p>newline-per-chained-call</p>

no-array-constructor
no-bitwise
no-continue
no-inline-comments
no-lonely-if
no-mixed-operators
no-multiple-empty-lines
no-negated-condition
no-nested-ternary
no-new-object
no-plusplus
no-restricted-syntax
no-tabs
no-ternary
no-trailing-spaces
no-underscore-dangle
no-unneeded-ternary
no-whitespace-before-property
object-curly-newline
object-curly-spacing
object-property-newline
one-var-declaration-per-line
one-var
operator-assignment
operator-linebreak
padded-blocks
quote-props
require-jsdoc
semi-spacing
semi
sort-keys
sort-vars
space-before-blocks
space-before-function-paren
space-in-parens
space-infix-ops
space-unary-ops
spaced-comment
unicode-bom
wrap-regex

Configurations for the category *ES6*

Uses	Does not use
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">arrow-body-stylearrow-parensarrow-spacingconstructor-supergenerator-star-spacingno-class-assignno-confusing-arrowno-const-assignno-dupe-class-membersno-duplicate-importsno-new-symbolno-restricted-importsno-this-before-superno-useless-computed-keyno-useless-constructorno-useless-renameno-varobject-shorthandprefer-arrow-callbackprefer-constprefer-destructuringprefer-numeric-literalsprefer-rest-paramsprefer-spreadprefer-templaterequire-yieldrest-spread-spacingsort-importssymbol-descriptiontemplate-curly-spacingyield-star-spacing

Configurations for the category *Strict Mode*

Uses	Does not use
	strict

Configurations for the category *NodeJS and CommonJS*

Uses	Does not use
	callback-return global-require handle-callback-err no-mixed-requires no-new-require no-path-concat no-process-env no-process-exit no-restricted-modules no-sync